

Performance Analysis of Low-Resolution Electroencephalogram Source Localization Techniques

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Received December 21, 2021; Revised January 31, 2022; Accepted February 09, 2022

Abstract

Brain source localization has attained significant fascination over the last few decades. Source localization in the human brain is a prospective complication that is derived in the multifaceted real-world complications because of the brain's practical and biological density, other than medical precincts of assembling Electroencephalogram (EEG) from enormously various subjects. It is validated that the electromagnetic signal recorded on the top of the scalp is owing to the collective actions of neurons inside the brain. Any impulsive action of the brain, sensory stimulus, cognitive action, or the generation of motor yield possibly will offer intensification to such neuronal actions. Source-localization in the human brain implicates the localization and detection of such primary neuronal originators into the brain. Although renowned and different research in the area, the complications remnants to be a mysterious inverse problem in the brain signal processing research. The performance of EEG source localization techniques based on standardized Low-Resolution Brain Electromagnetic Tomography (sLORETA) and exact Low-Resolution Brain Electromagnetic Tomography (eLORETA) is highlighted in this research. The Event-Related Potential (ERP) records with chromatic stimulus are considered for analysis at diverse time intervals for both techniques and final results are discussed in reports of scalp map, slice view, and, cortex map and proposed the optimum techniques for EEG source localization.

Index Terms: Electroencephalogram, Inverse problems, standardized Low-Resolution Brain Electromagnetic Tomography, exact Low-Resolution Brain Electromagnetic Tomography, Event-Related Potential.

I. INTRODUCTION

The absorption sensation of the head to investigate Roentgen rays branded biological particles or electrodes is particularly included in numerous methods such as glucose-absorption or dopamine-fusion [1]. The signals taken from the head are stimulated soon after the parental development after the seventeen and eighteen weeks also accordingly they illustrate the practicable of the intellect [2]. The combined study of brain actions and medical imaging methods is named 'Practical Neuroimaging'. The recognizing and understanding of the action of the anthropoid intellect is significantly intended for recognition identifying and dealing with numerous brain-ailments (for instance, epilepsy, tumor, alzheimer, schizophrenia, depression, and stress) and many other allied infections that were reported [3]. The classification of neuropsychological methods is settled to compute and categorize the Electromagnetic Motions (i.e., EM) into the brain as a result of numerous actions. These neuroimaging methods have precise possessions and therefore are utilized for different research and medical applications [4]. As stated by the literature accessible, the Electroencephalogram (EEG) is an easily accessible method with a low price for medical and

study applications in terms of high-temporal (in ms) resolution shadowed via MEG, nIRS, and PET correspondingly [5]. As the brain sources localization is grounded on the signals of the brain (electric potentials) taken via plate is termed EEG source-localization. The campaign was initiated about four decades back to resolute the problem related to brain source localization via associating the prevailing electro-anatomical body facts concerning the brain to essential values leading to the total current in the cranium. The electrode cap is used to obtain the EEG signal. EEG source-localization (i.e., EEG inverse-problem) that is not well-modeled mathematically. This point toward the number of identified factors (potentials obtained from the scalp) is constantly low than energetic sources [6]. Statistically, the method is supposed as poorly posed, if the system-matrix's singular values are falling off towards zero in the way as there is not any specific space in the singular value band [7]. The brain source approximation methods are usually characterized in two ways such as parametric approaches as well as imaging approaches [8]. The parametric actions utilize the supposition of signifying the sources as comparable current dipoles. Variegation components are in thousands on the

exterior of cortical is signified the utilization of current dipole. Hence, the sources-estimation is rectilinear in this case such as the merely unidentified dipolar genes in the variegation component. Such as the problem of source approximation was already revealed the under firming in nature, therefore, standard techniques are utilized to regulate the grade of leveling. Hence, when pondering either to utilize a fixed-dipole formation or spinning-dipole, with help of multidimensional reduction methods the sources are assessed. The approaches are ranging from starting Levenburg-Marquardt and global optimization algorithms to Nadler Meade downhill simplex considerations and simulated strengthening were mentioned. As stated above classification, several methods grounded upon subspace-factorization, Bayesian approaches, least-square principle, and limitation Laplacian have been established. These approaches are usually grounded upon Least Square Approximation (i.e., LSE) with least mean limitations (like least-mean established and expressed [9] and its improved version by Laplacian-smoothness (like Low-Resolution Brain Electromagnetic Tomography or LORETA [10], standardized Low-Resolution Brain Electromagnetic Tomography or sLORETA [11] and exact Low-Resolution Brain Electromagnetic Tomography or eLORETA [12, 13 14]) and a few other parametric-array signals-processing founded subspace approaches (Multiple Signal classifier (MUSIC) [15], Recursive-MUSIC, RAP- MUSIC were reported in the literature.

EEG source activity of visual motion imagery is localization method is used [16-18]. Numerous methods have been highlighted and discoursed for EEG brain source localization [19]. A new technique e sparse eLORETA for approximating a nonparametric way out to the source localization problem [20]. Spatial precision for EEG source localization measured by Local Autoregressive Average (LAURA), LORETA sLORETA, eLORETA was used [21].

Section II goes over the theory-related methods that have been utilized in this research, namely sLORETA and eLORETA, Section III goes over the methodology employed in this research, Section IV goes over the results and their discussions, and finally, the conclusion is given in Section V.

II. MATHEMATICAL BACKGROUND FOR sLORETA AND eLORETA

A. sLORETA

sLORETA is a more sophisticated version of LORETA that uses a low-resolution dispersed imaging approach to locate brain sources. The multiplication of current circulation through the brain volume is based on this method. In some applications, such as feature abstraction in Spatio-temporal pattern recognition, high resolution is necessary where LORETA's low spatial resolution is an issue. Ever since the enhancement of LORETA as sLORETA, eLORETA, WMN-LORETA [22], and many other methods are developed. The sLORETA is also pronounced as standardized LORETA, which is based on the theory of the current-density standardization, which indicates both biological variance in actual signal and

noise variance in EEG measurements is measured. The correspondence to the approach delivered has attained via localization method in which it is responsible for standardization way of the evaluations of current density. The functional for sLORETA can be represented in mathematical expression as [23-25]:

$$F = \|Y - LJ - c_1\|^2 + \alpha \|J\|^2 \quad (1)$$

Where:

$Y \in \mathfrak{R}^{N_c \times N_n}$, is the data-set acquired by N_c sensors and denotes the number of time samples.

$J \in \mathfrak{R}^{N_d \times N_n}$, is the current density accountable for the transmission of the energy of current-dipoles disseminated over the cortical surface.

Though, the data-set (Y) and the sources (J) are interrelated over L (gain-matrix) sometimes it is also labeled as lead field-matrix.

Hence the suppositions of zero mean Gaussian-noise $\in$. Here $\alpha \geq 0$ is the regularization parameter.

For a given lead field (L), voltage measurements (Y), and regularization parameter (α), this function is meant to be minimized about J and c :

$$J' = TY, \text{ with } T = L^T H [HLL^T H + \alpha H]^+ \quad (2)$$

Where:

$H \in \mathfrak{R}^{N_E \times N_E}$ is centering-matrix and is defined as:

$$H = I - \frac{11^T}{1^T 1} \quad (3)$$

However, $I \in \mathfrak{R}^{N_E \times N_E}$ is an identity matrix and $1 \in \mathfrak{R}^{N_E \times 1}$ is a vector of ones:

By utilizing an average reference for measurements, one can obtain the functional as:

$$F = \|Y - LJ\|^2 + \alpha \|J\|^2 \quad (4)$$

With the solution, as:

$$J' = TY, \text{ with } T = L^T [LL^T + \alpha H]^+$$

In this way the sources are estimated in presence and absence of noise. It was claimed in the research article [12] with different set-ups for EEG data that sLORETA estimates the current sources without any localization error i.e., exact solution with zero localization error. Hence, it was termed as the first-order source localization technique. The simulations with and without noise were carried out to prove the claim. As a result, it was proposed that sLORETA is superior to minimum-norm and Dale approaches in terms of quality. With various head modeling approaches, this technique has been used extensively for source localization. This approach is implemented using a variety of neuroimaging tools, such as NET STATION and LORETA. The sLORETA approach was used in several articles to locate the sources. The drawback of sLORETA is its limited resolution, which is attributable to solution regularization for stability. Also, sLORETA fails to localize several sources when the point-spread functions of sources overlap.

B. eLORETA

There are several convenient efforts are to reduce the localization error via taking the weight-matrix in a suitable mode. Therefore, [12], provides a more significant approach to reduce localization error up to 12 to 7 mm via attaining deepness weighting. The University of Zurich established this approach and verified it as a functioning project in 2005. It is revealed [12] that, eLORETA offers zero error in exact localization in the presence of both structured biological noise and measurement. Considering the generalized weighted minimum norm solution as below:

$$J' = TY \text{ With } T = W^{-1}L^T[LW^{-1}L^T + \alpha H]^+ \quad (5)$$

Where is symmetric weight matrix and $\alpha \geq 0$ is the regularization parameter as defined above?

A particular case is considered for weight matrix such that only it has non-zero diagonal entities that $W_i \in \mathfrak{R}^{3 \times 3}$.

Hence, for regularization parameter i.e., $\alpha = 0$, the estimated current-density at i^{th} voxel is given by:

$$j'_i = W_i^{-1}L_i^T[LW^{-1}L^T + \alpha H]^+ \quad (6)$$

Hence, with the solution equation as provided above, if the weights are defined as:

$$W_i = [L_i^T(LW^{-1}L^T + \alpha H)^+L_i]^{1/2} \quad (7)$$

Furthermore, the method which satisfies the weights provided by the equation is termed eLORETA which according to their originators is an exact method with zero localization error. Also, it should be noted that eLORETA is standardized like sLORETA which employs that its theoretical predictable variance is unity.

The simulations of the given approaches were done via friendly available academic eLORETA KEY software. The results observed that eLORETA is a reliable localizing technique with no localization bias, especially in the non-ideal state that offers zero error localization i.e. with noise. Several studies are providing a comparison between sLORETA and eLORETA which shows that eLORETA provides better results than sLORETA [13].

III. METHODOLOGY

The evaluation is done in between sLORETA and eLORETA via using functions accessible with sLORETA software. This program was created by the KEY Institute of Brain-Mind Research at the University Hospital of Psychiatry in Zurich, Switzerland. The ERP data, which is provided by Dr. Michaela-Esslen, Institute of Neuropsychology, University of Zurich, Switzerland, is used for evaluation in the sLORETA software. The data specifications are stated as: is visual ERP data indicates that it is collected via supplying the visual stimulus to applicants in terms of images of flowers. The sampled data with 256 Hz is kept in the record in a file list25e.txt with the name of the electrode. Overall 17 applicants are including seven males and ten females. The data is assembled into two sections, paired and non-paired. For paired ERP data, two chromatic incentives are supplied to

applicants that are, stimulation with images of flowers and grey screen respectively. Total 25 electrodes reserved with 256 Hz as the preferred sampling rate. The initial stage is the text file of the electrode with .txt extension is translated into Talairach-electrodes coordinates with, 'sxyz' extension. Then transformation matrix, which is either sLORETA or eLORETA transformation according to the need of request is generated from, 'sxyz' file. Once the transformation is done then the viewer-explorer utility of sLORETA software is loaded with the file. At that juncture, the ERP paired data is carefully chosen from the loaded file. The chosen data is tested and views the activation at different time instants in 3D cortex-map, Scalp-map, and Slice-viewer correspondingly. Finally, the active region is tested and contrasted for both approaches. At the time instants of 50.78, 136.7, 406.3, and 558.6 ms. the results are exposed with regards to regions activated with analogous maps. The analysis of sLORETA and eLORETA is done via similar software which generates the results of its and that are further reviewed in terms of visual merely. Though, both approaches are arranged in suitable captions.

IV. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The results are obtained via the methodology as defined above. As stated in the results, the activation of diverse brain areas for 50.78, 136.7, 406.3, and 558.6 ms, time instants were detected. The activation is reliant on both, the stimulus supplied and the applicant's attention for the period of the testing. At 50.78 ms time-instant, the stimulated-region is mostly happened to be the frontal region for sLORETA and eLORETA correspondingly. It seems no difference, there are some minor blurs are there in Figure 2 as compared to Figure 4. However, it can be visualized that activated results are created thru sLORETA have a lower resolution in contrast with eLORETA. eLORETA creates more-clearer and optimum facts of activation region in frontal as compared to sLORETA. This information may be verified by looking at the 3D scalp findings, which are shown in Figures 1 and Figures 3 for both techniques. Continuing the discussion for the second result where the time instant is kept at 136.78 ms, it can be seen that the temporal region is the most active area for both approaches. Figures. 5 and Figures 7 indicate that eLORETA can solve an inverse problem for active brain sources with high precision by suppressing unclear stimulations. Furthermore, though sLORETA localizes the active area with less precision as likened to eLORETA. As well, Figures. 6 and Figures 8 revealed the scalp map of sLORETA and eLORETA, in which it can be noted a more-clearer view with eLORETA as contrasted to sLORETA. The third result for both inverse approaches where the time instant kept at 406.30 ms, the respective stimulation maps are generated in Figures. 9 and Figures 11 correspondingly. In this case, the parietal region is the most active. The results of eLORETA have exact localization with more precision through eliminating a reduced amount of important stimulation and thus reducing localization error. The scalp maps at 406.30 ms are generated in Figures 10 and Figures 12 correspondingly. At 558.6 ms, the time instant for both sLORETA and eLORETA are highly activated in the parietal region as

Figures 13 and Figures 15 reveal themselves for both sLORETA and eLORETA. It demonstrates clearer stimulation for eLORETA as contrasted to sLORETA and also it is useable for the scalp map for both approaches as revealed in Figures 14 and Figures 16. It is obvious in the lights of results that the performance of eLORETA is a more precise and clear vision with poor localization error. Furthermore, however, sLORETA offers the stimulation maps presenting stimulation in similar regions as with eLORETA but has not got resolution as eLORETA has got. Thus, eLORETA can be regarded as the best choice among low resolution approaches for instance LORETA and sLORETA.

Figure 1: Activation map for sLORETA at 50.78ms

Figure 2: Scalp map for sLORETA at 50.78ms

Figure 3: Activation map for eLORETA at 50.78ms

Figure 4: Scalp map for eLORETA at 50.78ms

Figure 5: Activation map for sLORETA at 136.7ms

Figure 6: Scalp map for sLORETA at 136.7ms

Figure 7: Activation map for eLORETA at 136.7ms

Figure 8: Scalp map for eLORETA at 136.7ms

Figure 9: Activation map for sLORETA at 406.3ms

Figure 10: Scalp map for sLORETA at 406.3ms

Figure 11: Activation map for eLORETA at 406.3ms

Figure 12: Scalp map for eLORETA at 406.3ms

Figure 13: Activation map for sLORETA at 558.6ms

Figure 14: Scalp map for sLORETA at 558.6ms

Figure 15: Activation map for sLORETA at 558.6ms

Figure 16: Scalp map for eLORETA at 558.6ms

Table 1: Comparison of EEG localization algorithms

S. No.	Method	Author	Merits	Demerits
1	sLORETA [11]	R.D. Pascual (2002)	Provide precise zero-error localization	Poor performance and blurring have been reported due to instability
2	eLORETA [12]	R.D. Pascual (2007)	Method for precise localization with zero localization error	Image blurring has been seen as a result of regularizations

V. CONCLUSION

A comparison of binary low-resolution brain source localization techniques (i.e., sLORETA and eLORETA) is presented in this article. The ERP data from seventeen applicants was obtained with chromatic reward provided during assessment using sLORETA freeware created by The KEY Institute of Brain-Mind Research of University Hospital of Psychiatry, Switzerland. The evaluation was done by considering the capability of the localization for sLORETA and eLORETA algorithms through visual inspection of both stimulations as well as scalp maps. It was shown through comparison that eLORETA carry out in a superior approach with luminous and less localization error feature of result for localizing the sources as contrasted to sLORETA. Furthermore, LORETA has the greater capability of crushing less important sources as contrasted to sLORETA. Therefore, it can be determined that for EEG/ERP facts at slightly disorder action (for instance chromatic incentive, acoustic incentive, etc.), eLORETA achieves better outcomes among low resolution approaches for instance LORETA and sLORETA. The study is valid for clinical applications such as diagnoses of various brain disorders. The example includes the

localization of epileptic foci for epileptic. Also, surgical applications, this study can be applied for unaggressive localization of epileptogenic regions in patients with fractional confiscations.

Acknowledgement

The authors would like to thank Indus University, Karachi, Pakistan, and DHA Suffa University, Karachi, Pakistan for all the support provided to accomplish this research work.

Authors Contributions

Muhammad Mubashir's contribution to this study was the concept, technical implementation, and correspondence. The methodology to conduct this research work was proposed by Chandar Kumar. Data collection and supervision were performed by Shubash Kumar. Areeb Anis Khan facilitated the data compilation and validation. Zain Abidi contribution was project administration, and paper writing.

Conflict of Interest

There is no conflict of interest between all the authors.

Data Availability Statement

No testing data is available in this paper.

Funding

This research received no external funding.

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